

Glacial Flour as a Source of Nutrients: A horizon scan of key themes and opportunities

Discussion Meeting and Workshop, British Antarctic Survey, Cambridge UK

Aurora Centre, March 17-19th 2026

Background and introduction

Glaciers were once thought to be inert environments, too cold for biology or for chemical reactions to occur. It's only in the last two decades that we've discovered that glacial environments are "hot spots" for biogeochemical processes that release biologically important elements. As glaciers flow, they crush the underlying rock into very fine "flour". When this material reacts with water flowing beneath glaciers and ice sheets, the unusual chemical conditions allow new, solid materials to form. These very fine particles are highly reactive and can release elements and compounds into the environment. Glacial flour is an important source of critical nutrients for coastal marine environments and has attracted substantial interest as a fertiliser for crops, but also has the potential to harbour toxic metals. With the growing interest in the use of glacial flour as a resource, and in the face of a changing climate, we need a better understanding of how glaciers impact carbon and nutrient cycling, and ecosystems.

Different research groups are working on disentangling how different elements are released as these particles flow downstream and how they interact with each other. The aim of this workshop was to bring scientists from these different laboratories together with other stakeholders for knowledge exchange and networking, and to produce a horizon scan of the key gaps in our understanding of how glacial flour feeds biology in marine and terrestrial systems.

Key themes

The workshop discussions highlighted four key themes:

Understanding the interaction between glacial flour and its chemical environment

- Defining **what we mean by “glacial flour”** and how it changes as it transitions from subglacial sediment to suspended sediment to bedload and bank deposits, and into the sedimentary record.
- Understanding the **reactivity and bioavailability** of glacial flour across lithologies, size fractions (including colloids) and across freshwater and glacio-marine environments.
- Evaluating the role that glacial flour, its production, and the subglacial environment, play in chemical reactions fundamental to **metabolic processes**.

Understanding connectivity, glacial flour transport and nutrient pathways

- Improving our understanding of connectivity between **subglacial systems, proglacial groundwater, rivers and lakes, and fjords**.
- Calculating the fluxes of **dissolved vs. particulate** nutrient exports and how their importance changes over a range of transport distances and timescales.
- Mapping and quantifying the **longevity and downstream transport** distance of glacial flour into the ocean.
- Assessing and quantifying the potential for **benthic storms** to resuspend nutrient-rich particulates in glacierised fjords and coastal environments.
- Understanding **physical oceanographic processes** that connect glacial inputs to downstream systems.

Understanding the biogeochemical and ecological impacts of glacial flour

- Distinguishing **direct vs. indirect supply** of glacial nutrients, metals and organic compounds, and how these change under climate change.
- Understanding the influence of glacial flour on **phytoplankton, zooplankton, and higher trophic levels**.
- Assessing whether **extreme ecological events** (e.g., harmful algal blooms, mass zooplankton die-offs) interact with, or are impacted by, glacial processes.
- Evaluating the impact of changing **(pro-)glacial lake environments** for ecosystems.
- Disentangling the effects of **glacier retreat and transition from marine-terminating to land-terminating** states on fjord ecosystems.
- Evaluating the impact of deglaciation on **proglacial landscape expansion** and ecosystem changes.
- Understanding the impacts of **complete glacier loss** on biogeochemical cycling and ecosystems.

Understanding glacial flour as a resource, including potential applications and risks

- Evaluating the importance of glacial environments to **society** as freshwater sources and contributors to fisheries.
- Investigating the role of glacial flour as a source of (micro)nutrients for **enhancing ocean productivity**.
- Investigating the use of glacial flour for **enhanced rock weathering** as a carbon dioxide removal (CDR) method.
- Understanding the use of glacial flour as a **soil fertiliser** in agriculture, including benefits and risks to downstream rivers and coastal oceans.
- Assessing **knowledge gaps around efficacy** of carbon uptake, scalability, ecological risks, and regulatory needs.

Key opportunities

Throughout the workshop discussions, important experimental and methodological gaps were identified, **providing opportunities for future collaborative research** including the need for:

- Investigation of a broad range of inorganic and organic components, in addition to key limiting nutrients.
- Standardisation of incubation experiments and sequential sediment extractions.
- In situ observations (which have been fully assessed for impact and risk) to complement incubation experiments.
- Greater interaction between scientists in field and laboratory-based observation, Earth Observation (EO), and modellers.
- Greater interaction between environmental scientists, social scientists, and humanities to ensure a holistic view of how glacial flour is used as a resource.

To address these research gaps, there is a clear need for multidisciplinary approaches, **providing opportunities for multidisciplinary collaborations** between glaciologists, limnologists and marine biogeochemists with:

- Hydrologists and physical oceanographers, to map and quantify water circulation and connectivity.
- Experts in EO (use of satellite, drones and other airborne platforms), to scale up observations.
- Modellers, to scale up from localised observations to regional to global impacts, and improve mechanistic understanding of processes.
- Palaeoclimatologists, to provide insights into long-term links between sediment histories and climate, and analogues of potential future scenarios in the geological record.
- Indigenous rightsholders in regions where the glacial flour is sourced, to fully coproduce research and development.
- Social scientists and political geographers, to assess the societal impacts of using glacial flour as a resource.
- Other stakeholders of applications of glacial flour including the agricultural industry, farmers and the fishing industry.
- Engineering geologists and industrial geochemists, to assess the interplay between nutrient supply and sediment management.
- Aquatic and marine engineers and technology developers, to develop novel methodologies for autonomous observations.
- Astrobiologists, to evaluate the potential of subglacial processes and glacial flour as proxies for reactions fundamental to the origin of life on this and other planets.
- Experts in “third pole” regions such as Himalayas, Andes, and Patagonia, to ensure a full range of physical and human geographic conditions are assessed.

Appendix 1: Workshop scope

This workshop is funded by the United Kingdom's Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Office (FCDO)'s "Supporting Impactful UK Arctic Science Engagement Scheme 2025-2026", administered through the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) Arctic Office. The purpose of the scheme is to support effective engagement that aligns with the interests of some, or all, of the six Arctic Council Working Groups, and the priorities of The Kingdom of Denmark's Chairship of the Arctic Council. The project was funded through a competitive, open call, and will report independently to the FCDO, Arctic Office and Arctic Council Working Groups (specifically Protection of the Arctic Marine Environment (PAME), Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna (CAFF), and the Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP)).

Appendix 2: Workshop schedule

Tuesday March 17th

- 14:00 Welcome
- 14:10 Keynote talk: Jon Hawkings (UPenn, USA)
- 14:45 Session 1: Subglacial processes
Mark Skidmore (UStockholm, Sweden)
Beatriz Gill Olivas (AarhusU, Denmark)
- 15:20 Coffee break
- 16:00 Session 2: Environments on, in and under glaciers
Martyn Tranter (AarhusU, Denmark)
Klara Köhler (AarhusU, Denmark)
- 16:30 Discussion
- 17:30 Close

Wednesday March 18th

- 09:00 Welcome
- 09:05 Session 3: Elemental interactions
Rhiannon Jones (BAS, UK)
Jeff Paolo Perez (GFZ, Germany)
- 09:30 Discussion
- 10:30 Coffee break
- 11:00 Session 4: Downstream biogeochemistry
Guillaume Lamarch-Gagnon (UiT, Norway)
Laura Rasmussen (UiT, Norway)
Silje Waaler (UiT, Norway)
- 11:45 Discussion
- 12:30 Working lunch break
- 14:00 Session 5: Novel technologies: remote sensing and modelling
Sandra Arndt (Université Libre de Bruxelles, Belgium)
Ben Wallis (University of Leeds, UK)

15:00 Close

Thursday March 19th

09:00 Welcome

09:05 Session 6: Ecological impacts
Philipp Assmy (NPI, Norway)
Colin Sinclair (UiT, Norway)
Kara Sempell (UGrenoble, Switzerland)
Malgorzata Rizzi (UCPH, Denmark)

10:05 Discussion and introduction to "essay questions"

10:30 Coffee break

11:00 Breakout groups to discuss "essay questions"

12:30 Feedback from working group rapporteurs

13:00 Working lunch break

14:00 Close

Appendix 3: Workshop participants and joint report authors

Sandra Arndt, Université Libres de Bruxelles, Belgium
Philipp Assmy, Norwegian Polar Institute, Norway
Caitlin Banbury, University of Durham, UK
Beatriz Gill Olivas, Aarhus University, Denmark
Jonathan Hawkings, University of Pennsylvania, USA
Katharine Hendry, British Antarctic Survey, UK
Catherine Hirst, University of Durham, UK (remote attendance)
Rhiannon Jones, British Antarctic Survey, UK
Emma Kocik, University of Pennsylvania, USA
Klara Köhler, Aarhus University, Denmark
Guillaume Lamarche-Gagnon, The Arctic University of Norway, Norway
Jeffrey Paulo H. Perez, GFZ Potsdam, Germany
Helena Pryer, University of Cambridge, UK
Laura Helene Rasmussen, The Arctic University of Norway, Norway
Malgorzata Rizzi, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
Ricarda Runte, The Arctic University of Norway, Norway
Kara Sampsell, University of Grenoble, Switzerland
Colin Sinclair, The Arctic University of Norway, Norway
Mark Skidmore, Stockholm University, Sweden
Martyn Tranter, Aarhus University, Denmark
Joost Martijn van Genuchten, The Arctic University of Norway, Norway
Silje Waaler, The Arctic University of Norway, Norway
Jemma Wadham, The Arctic University of Norway, Norway
Ben Wallis, University of Leeds, UK